

Gender Roles in North Cyprus: A Discourse Analytic Approach

By

Feriha Dikmen and Huseyin Bozdoglar

Girne American University, Cyprus (Northern)

Abstract

Using a Discourse Analytic approach this research sets out to understand the perception and interpretation of gender representation in Turkish television adverts by Turkish Cypriot viewers. In particular it sought to understand the degree of gender sensitivity and generational differences among Turkish Cypriot viewers. A sample cutting across all generational categories was interviewed and their responses analyzed for cues. As a general outcome of our study, it is found out that the perception of gender roles used in advertisement differs depending on the age and gender of people.

Key words: *tv adverts, gender representation, gender roles, cultivation of ideas, consumerism*

2016 © AFREAPS°

Introduction

The use of advertisement in the development of societal value systems is nothing novel. It is a practice which involves the infusion of and reinforcement of recognizable societal norms into the development of acceptable messages and scenarios which resonates with the general populace in a bid to create a push factor that leads to the acquisition of products. However despite the primary aim of such adverts being the acquisition of products, there lies inherently a mechanism for influencing an effecting social change. It is the ability to influence social behavior that makes this study relevant especially with regard to the Turkish Cypriot community, where no research of a similar nature does exist. To go about achieving the objective of this study the key research question posed goes thus: What is the profile of Northern Cypriot viewers' perception of gender representation in Turkish television adverts by Northern Cypriot viewers? To derive answers to this question, the following five sub research questions were posed:

- 1- Is there a generation-specific difference in the perception of gender representation in Turkish television adverts?
- 2- Does perception of gender representation in Turkish television adverts by distinct generations reflect an altered gender-sensitivity in Northern Cyprus society?

- 3- What is the profile of opinion of Northern Cypriot viewers about the influence of television adverts on construction of gender roles?
- 4- Does gender representation in Turkish television adverts effect consumer behaviour of Northern Cyprus viewers?
- 5- Is there a gender-specific difference in the effects of gender representation in Turkish television adverts on consumer behaviour of North Cyprus viewers?

Also relying on extant research carried out in far removed geographic locations other than North Cyprus, the following main hypothesis will be tested using the discourse analytic approach. **H₁**: Hypothesis of this dissertation is; “the profile of current viewer (Northern Cypriot) perception of gender representation in television advertisements reflects a gender-sensitive society”.

Discourse Analysis

It is possible to describe discourse as a way of understanding the world and aspects of the world. Discourse analysis is all about why and how individuals use their language in specific social circumstances in its rights. It illustrates how language could be changeable or reproducible while using in social world or to find out in social world with similarities and constructing forms and text of our language (Phillips and Hardy, 2002). The word discourse mentions about two main points “what does the text producer mean in the text and what does the text mean to the receiver” (Widdowson 2007, p. 7). As Widdowson points out human produce texts, to get ideas, belief, explain something and give a message across and get other humans to think about these messages or think in certain ways (Widdowson 2007). In order way of explaining discourse is sense-making history. According to Locke (1990), discourse is accepted as a reflection of human signs and verbal language in making sense of the world and aspects. According to Teun van Dijk (1998), discourse is attached with socio-cognitive theory in historical approaches, Wodak and Meyer (2009) notes that discourse relies on oral utterances or written document as a “structured forms of knowledge”. Wood and Kroger (2000, p. 33) carries out that discourse analysis “is not just the coding it is much more than this, it is the assessment of relationship between coding categories”. Gender is also a part of discourse. Gender is a social effect of biological variables, it is a part of individuals.

In this study the responses collected from the interviews were scanned for the coding categories and the context and the meaning of each coding word were analysed through dictionary definitions of the code words.

Discourse of General Responses to All Questions

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed most frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 7 (consumerism) (which contains the words buying/purchasing, influence, biased, effect, advertising, branding, trust). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Buy/Purchase:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*buy*” as:

- 1- To obtain sth by paying money for it.
- 2- To be enough to pay for sth.
- 3- Persuade sb to do sth dishonest in return for money.
- 4- To obtain sth by losing sth else of great value.
- 5- To believe that sth is true, especially sth that is not very likely.

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*purchase*” as:

- 1- The act or process of buying sth: to make a purchase.
- 2- Something that you have bought.
- 3- A firm hold on sth with the hands or feet, for example when you are climbing.

In the responses the word “*buy/purchase*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1 for the word 'buy' and definitions 1 and 2 for the word 'purchase'. For example the statement “*Perhaps, if there is a brand which develops a fixation on me, it would not alter my purchasing/buying habits but may revoke sympathy*”(man 40+). As another example “*Feeling the quality of a product in a commercial affects my purchasing/buying behaviour*”(woman 18-25). As another example “*In general, TV commercials change my buying/puchasing habits*”

(man 18-25). In addition “*Commercials extensively alter peoples' purchasing habits*” (woman 18-25).

Table 1. Discourse Analysis of Code Consumerism (buy/purchase)

“ <i>Belki takıldığım bir marka varsa satın alma alışkanlıklarımı değiştirmez ama bir sempati uyandırır</i> ” (erkek 40+)	The act or process of buying sth: to make a purchase.
“ <i>Reklamda ürünün kalitesini hissettiğim için satın almam etkilenir</i> ”. (kadin 18-25)	The act or process of buying sth: to make a purchase.
“ <i>Tv de izlediğim reklamlar genel olarak satın alma alışanlığımı değiştirir</i> ”. (erkek 18-25)	The act or process of buying sth: to make a purchase.
“ <i>İnsanların satın alma alışkanlığının büyük bir bölümü reklamlarla değişir</i> ”.(kadin 18-25)	To believe that sth is true, especially sth that is not very likely

Influence:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*influence*” as:

- 1- The effect that sb/sth has on the way a person thinks or behaves or on the way that sth works or develops.
- 2- The power that sb/sth has to make sb/sth behave in a particular way.
- 3- A person or thing that affects the way a person behaves and thinks.

In the responses, the word “*influence*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1, 2 and 3 interchangeably. For example the statement “*The commercials that we see on the television, listen on the radio or see on billboards, magazines or newspapers are surely imbedded in our subconscious and affect us no matter what*” (man 18-25). As another example “*Since I as a consumer also care about the financial aspect of the issue, the commercials with a campaign slogan have much more impact*”(man 40+).

Table 2. Discourse Analysis of Code Consumerism (influence)

<p>“Elbette televizyonda izlediğimiz, radyoda dinlediğimiz yada billboardlarda, dergilerde yada gazetelerde gördüğümüz reklamlar istemesek dahi bir şekilde bilinç altımıza girmektedir ve bizi etkilemektedir”. (erkek 18-25)</p>	<p>1- The effect that sb/sth has on the way a person thinks or behaves or on the way that sth works or develops.</p> <p>2- The power that sb/sth has to make sb/sth behave in a particular way.</p> <p>3- A person or thing that affects the way a person behaves and thinks.</p>
<p>“Bir tüketici olarak maddi boyutuyla da ilgilendiğimden bir kampanya sloganıyla hareket eden reklamların etkisi çok daha büyük”. (erkek 40 +)</p>	<p>1- The effect that sb/sth has on the way a person thinks or behaves or on the way that sth works or develops.</p> <p>2- The power that sb/sth has to make sb/sth behave in a particular way.</p> <p>3- A person or thing that affects the way a person behaves and thinks.</p>

Biased:

In the responses the word “*biased*” has not been used in a context.

Effect:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*effect*” as:

- 1- A change that sb/sth else; a result: the effect of heat on metal
- 2- A particular look, sound or impression that sb, such as an artist or a writer, wants to create.
- 3- Your personal possessions.

In the responses the word “*effect*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*With the use of child figure and voiceover in commercial, it is aimed to create an impact on the viewers*” (man 18-25). As another example “*It is tried to make an effect*

on families by underlining the keeping food fresh in the fridge and making savings” (man 40 +). Moreover “The figure of baby always awakes the attention on me” (woman 40 +). In addition “The commercial affects the viewers in a positive and negative way” (woman 18-25).

Table 3. Discourse Analysis of Code Consumerism (effect)

“Reklamda çocuk figürünün kullanılması ve seslendirme yapılmasında izleyicilerin etkilenmesi amaçlanmıştır”. (erkek 18-25)	A change that sb/sth else; a result: the effect of heat on mental
“Buzdolabında yiyeceklerin taze kalması ile tasarruf sağlanması vurgulanarak aileler üzerinde etki yaratmaya çalışılmıştır” (erkek 40+)	A change that sb/sth else; a result: the effect of heat on mental
“Bebek figürü her zaman bende etki uyandırmıştır”. (kadin 40 +)	A change that sb/sth else; a result: the effect of heat on mental
“Reklam izleyicileri olumlu ve olumsuz etkiler. (kadin 18-25)	A change that sb/sth else; a result: the effect of heat on mental

Advertising:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “advertising” as:

- 1- A notice, picture or film telling people about a product, job or service.
- 2- An example of sth that shows its good qualities.
- 3- The act of advertising sth and making it public.
- 4- The activity and industry of advertising things to people on television, newspaper, on the internet etc.

In the responses the word “advertising” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1 and 2. For example the statement “In these commercials, the firm of Beko is shown as the best and best-selling company of the world” (woman 18-25). In addition “The commercials that I watch mainly mean a lot to the target group; first of all, the most eye catching aspect of it is a family and the baby, the littlest member of that family, very creative and different commercial. The series of commercials knowing the target group that introduce the trust, quality, guarantee

and most importantly the longevity to the public” (man 40 +). Another statement “An adorable child is used in commercials which has made the product much attractive. The commercial has become consistent with the same person in all series of Beko commercial” (man 18-25). Another example “These commercials interpret the level of modern lifestyle” (woman 40 +). Moreover “Luxury consumption and practicality are highlighted in Beko commercials” (woman 18-25).

Table 4. Discourse Analysis of Code Consumerism (advertising)

“Bu reklamlarda Beko firmasının dünyanın en iyi ve en çok satan firması olduğu gösterilmektedir”. (kadin 18-25)	A notice, picture or film telling people about a product, job or service An example of sth that shows its good qualities.
“Genel anlamda izlediğim reklamlar hedef kitleye çok şeyi ifade ediyor, öncelikle en çok dikkat çeken tarafı bir aile ve ailenin en küçük ferdi olan bebek, çok yaratıcı ve farklı bir reklam. Hedef kitleyi tanımış reklamlar zinciri ve halka tam anlamıyla güveni, kaliteyi, garantiyi, en önemlisi uzun ömürlülüğü dile getiriyor”. (erkek 40 +)	A notice, picture or film telling people about a product, job or service An example of sth that shows its good qualities.
“Reklamlarda sevimli bir çocuk kullanılmış. Bu reklamlardaki ürünün daha çekici olmasını sağlamıştır. (erkek 18-25)	A notice, picture or film telling people about a product, job or service
“Bu reklamlar modern yaşam tarzının geldiği noktayı yorumlamaktadır”. (kadin 40 +)	A notice, picture or film telling people about a product, job or service
“Beko reklamlarında lüks tüketim ve kolaylık vurgulanmıştır”. (kadin 18-25)	A notice, picture or film telling people about a product, job or service

Branding:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “branding” as:

- 1- A type of product made by a particular company.
- 2- A particular type or kind of sth.
- 3- A mark made with a piece of hot metal, especially on farm animals to show who owns them.
- 4- The activity of giving a particular name and image to goods and services so that people will be attracted to them and want to buy them.

In the responses the word “branding” has been used in a context which parallels definitions 1 and 4. For example the statement “*Stating that Beko brand is a world brand and emphasizing the slogan of it’s smart while talking about the quality of products have stood out*”(man 40+). As another example “*It shows me the trust, quality, guarantee, durability by its saying of because it’s beko and especially being the most favorite brand in England as it’s a worldwide know brand*” (woman 18-25). In addition “*Also since it is the most selling brand of England, people change it as our society is always European wannabe*” (woman 18-25). As another example “*All commercials lead people to be brand slaves; so people move towards branding*” (woman 40 +).

Table 5. Discourse Analysis of Code Consumerism (branding)

<p>“<i>Ürünlerin kalitesinden bahsederken Beko markasının bir dünya markası olduğu ve akıllı o sloganının vurgulanması dikkat çekmiştir</i>”. (erkek 40 +)</p>	<p>A type of product made by a particular company The activity of giving a particular name image to goods and services so that people will be attracted to them and want to buy them.</p>
<p>“<i>Bana güveni, kaliteyi, garantiyi uzun ömürlülüğü çünkü o Beko diyerek ve özellikle İngiltere’de en çok tercih edilen marka diyerek yurt dışına açılmış ve tanınmış bir marka olduğunu da gösteriyor</i>”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>A type of product made by a particular company The activity of giving a particular name image to goods and services so that people will be attracted to them and want to buy them.</p>
<p>“<i>Ayrıca İngilterenin en çok satan markası olması nedeniyle insanlarımız zaten hep Avrupa markası özentsisi olduğu içinde değişir</i>”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>A type of product made by a particular company The activity of giving a particular name and image to goods and services so that people will be attracted to them and want to buy them.</p>
<p>“<i>Butür reklamlar insanların marka meraklısı olmaya yöneliyor ve bu sayade insan markalaşmaya yöneliyor</i>”. (kadın 40 +)</p>	<p>A type of product made by a particular company The activity of giving a particular name and image to goods and services so that people will be attracted to them and want to buy them.</p>

Trust:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “trust” as:

- 1- The belief that sb/sth is good, sincere, honest, etc. and will not try to harm trick you.

- 2- An arrangement by which an organization or a group of people has legal control of money or property that has been given to sb, usually until that person reaches a particular age; an amount of money or property that is controlled in this way.
- 3- An organization or a group of people that invests money that is given or lent to it and uses the profits to help a charity.
- 4- A group of companies that work together illegally to reduce competition, control prices, etc.

In the responses the word “*trust*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*When I’ve watched the commercial, I’ve trusted it and the brand*” (woman 18-25). As another example “*Especially the relationship between the mother and child in Beko commercials give a significant trust to the viewers*” (woman 40 +). Moreover “*The importance of cleanness is emphasized in commercials which try to prove the reliability of the brand Beko*” (man 18-25).

Table 6. Discourse Analysis of Code Consumerism (trust)

“ <i>Reklamı izleyince reklama ve markaya güvendim</i> ” (kadin 18-25)	The belief that sb/sth is good, sincere, honest, etc. and will not try to harm trick you.
“ <i>Özellikle Beko reklamında anne ve çocuk arasındaki ilişki izleyene inanılmaz güven veriyor</i> ”. (kadin 40 +)	The belief that sb/sth is good, sincere, honest, etc. and will not try to harm trick you.
“ <i>Temizliğin önemide reklamda vurgulanır ve bu reklamlarda Beko markasının güvenilirliğini ıspatlamaya çalışır</i> ”. (erkek 18-25)	The belief that sb/sth is good, sincere, honest, etc. and will not try to harm trick you.

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed second frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 2 (femininity) (which contains the words women, housewife, female, mother, beauty, wife, passive, business women). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Women:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*women*” as:

- 1- An adult female human: *men, women, children*

- 2- Female humans in general: (*informal*)(= has qualities that are typical of women)
- 3- A women who comes from the place mentioned or whose job or interest is connected with the thing mentioned: *an Englishwoman, Businesswomen,*
- 4- Female worker, especially one who works with her hands.
- 5- A rude way of addressing a female person in an angry or important way.
- 6- A wife or sexual partner.

In the responses the word “*women*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1 and 2. For example the statement “*The special relation of woman with the child is maintained in the commercials*” (*woman 18-25*). As another example “*The representation of woman at home is delivered in all commercials of Beko among all products where woman is in the kitchen*” (*man 40 +*). As another statement “*Not only for this commercial but in all white good commercials, the woman who spend the longest time in the kitchen, is used because kitchen and woman are accepted as a whole worldwide*” (*woman 40 +*).

Table 7. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (women)

“ <i>Kadının çocukla olan özel yakınlığı da reklamlarda korunmuştur</i> ”. (<i>kadin 18-25</i>)	An adult female human: men, women, children Female humans in general: (<i>informal</i>)(= has qualities that are typical of women)
“ <i>Beko reklamlarının bütün ürünlerinde mutfakta bir kadının olması kadının evdeki temsilini anlatmış</i> ”. (<i>erkek 40 +</i>)	An adult female human: men, women, children Female humans in general: (<i>informal</i>)(= has qualities that are typical of women)
“ <i>Sadece bu reklam için değil tüm beyaz eşya reklamlarında mutfakta en çok vakit geçiren kadın figürü kullanılır. Çünkü mutfak ve kadın tüm dünyada bir bütün olarak kabul edilir</i> ”. (<i>kadin 40 +</i>)	An adult female human: men, women, children Female humans in general: (<i>informal</i>)(= has qualities that are typical of women)

Housewife:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*housewife*” as:

- 1- A woman who stays at home to cook, clean, take care of the children and etc. while her husband or partner goes out to work.

In the responses the word “housewife” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*We can see that woman is a housewife and her duty is looking after children, cooking, washing the dishes and doing the laundry*” (man 40 +). As another example “*In today’s commercials, we can see that woman is not a housewife anymore, she is a working person*” (woman 18-25). Moreover “*It was not possible to see a man helping the housewife at home either in commercials or real life; however, women now also work and shares her household duties with her husband*” (woman 40 +). In addition “*Under today’s conditions, women are not only housewives. We clearly see this in commercials*” (man 18-25).

Table 8. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (housewife)

“ <i>Kadının ev kadını olduğu ve işinin çocuk bakmama yemek yapmak bulaşık ve çamaşır yıkamak olduğunu görebiliriz</i> ”. (erkek 40 +)	A woman who stays at home to cook, clean, take care of the children and etc. while her husband or partner goes out to work.
“ <i>Günümüz reklamlarında kadının artık ev hanımı değil de çalışan bir bayan olduğunu görmekteyiz</i> ”. (kadin 18-25)	A woman who stays at home to cook, clean, take care of the children and etc. while her husband or partner goes out to work.
“ <i>Eskiden biz ev hanımlarına erkeğin evde yardım etmesi ne reklamlarda ne de gerçek hayatta görülmekteydi, fakat günümüz koşullarında kadın da artık çalışıyor ve evdeki iş görevlerini eşiyile paylaşıyor</i> ”. (kadin 40 +)	A woman who stays at home to cook, clean, take care of the children and etc. while her husband or partner goes out to work.
“ <i>Günümüz koşullarında kadın artık sadece ev hanımı değil. Bunu da net bir şekilde reklamlarda da izlemekteyiz</i> ”. (erkek 18-25)	A woman who stays at home to cook, clean, take care of the children and etc. while her husband or partner goes out to work.

Female:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*female*” as:

- 1- Being a woman or a girl.
- 2- Of the sex that can lay eggs or given birth to babies.
- 3- Of women; typical of women; affecting women.
- 4- (*biology*) (of plants and flowers) that can produce fruits.
- 5- (*technical*) (of electrical equipment) having a hole that another part fits into.

In the responses the word “female” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1 and 2. For example the statement “*In the commercial that we watched, I observe that the responsibilities of woman have increased after the marriage and especially becoming a mother*” (woman 18-25). Furthermore “*I can see that women are relatively more responsible than men at the house chores after the marriage*” (woman 18-25).

Table 9. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (female)

<p>“<i>İzlediğimiz reklamlarda kadının evlendikten sonra ve özellikle anne olduktan sonra sorumluluklarının arttığını gözlemlemekteyim</i>”. (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>Being a woman or a girl. Of the sex that can lay eggs or given birth to babies.</p>
<p>“<i>İzlediğim reklamlarda kadının evlendikten sonra erkeğe nazaran daha fazla ev işlerinden sorumlu olduğunu görmekteyim</i>”. (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>Being a woman or a girl. Of the sex that can lay eggs or given birth to babies.</p>

Mother:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*mother*” as:

- 1- a female parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as a mother to a child.
- 2- the title of a women who is head of a female religious community.

In the responses the word “mother” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the *statement* “*Since mothers care about the health, nursing and hygiene of their children, a family environment and mother-child relationship are highlighted*” (man 40 +). As another example “*The only expectation of the baby is to be with the mother and spend time with*

her since mother is more responsible for the care of” (woman 40 +). Moreover “Even in today’s conditions, the reality that mother is the person who is responsible for the health, care and comfort of child is delivered to the consumer” (woman 18-25). Furthermore “The system coming from past to present; house chores, kitchen chores, child care are always delivered as mother’s duty” (man 40 +). In addition “The main message to be delivered in these 4 commercials is the sensitivity of mothers towards their children” (man 18-25).

Table 10. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (mother)

<i>“Özellikle anneler çocukların sağlıklarıyla, bakımlarıyla ve temizliğiyle ilgilendikleri için bir aile ortamı ve anne çocuk ilişkisi ön planda tutulmuştur” (erkek 40 +).</i>	a female parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as a mother to a child.
<i>“Bebeğin tek beklentisi anne ile beraber olup vakit geçirmektir, çünkü çocuğun bakımından daha fazla anne sorumludur”. (kadin 40 +)</i>	a female parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as a mother to a child.
<i>“Günümüz koşullarında bile reklamlarda annenin çocuğunun sağlığından, bakımından ve rahatlığından sorumlu kişi olması gerektiği izlenimi gerçeği tüketiciye aktarılır”. (kadin 18-25)</i>	a female parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as a mother to a child.
<i>“Geçmişten günümüze kadar gelen sistem; ev işleri, mutfak işeri, çocuk bakımı hep anneye ait gibi gösterilmektedir”. (erkek 40 +)</i>	a female parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as a mother to a child.
<i>“Bu 4 reklamda da verilmek istenen ana mesaj mesaj annelerin çocuklarına karşı olan hassasiyetidir”. (erkek 18-25)</i>	a female parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as a mother to a child.

Beauty:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*beauty*” as:

- 1- The quality of being pleasing to the senses or to the mind.
- 2- A person or thing that is beautiful.
- 3- An excellent example of its type.
- 4- A pleasing feature.

In the responses the word “*beauty*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1 and 4. For example the statement “*The company has used the baby very*” (woman 18-25). As another example “*It shows that there are products for the health of users, importance of time, cooking quickly and saving time for people*” (man 18-25). Furthermore “*I want to buy the best quality, functional and brand when buying*” (woman 18-25). Moreover “*Normally the features of no frost or A class were been looked for when a fridge was purchased; now many features are introduced to us as we see in commercials with the development of technology*” (man 18-25).

Table 11. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (beauty)

“ <i>Firma bebeği reklam için gayet güzel kullanmıştır</i> ”. (kadin 18-25)	The quality of being pleasing to the senses or to the mind. A pleasing feature.
“ <i>Kullanıcıların sağlığını, zamanın önemini, kısa sürede güzel yemekler yapmayı, kişilere daha fazla zaman kazandıran ürünler olduğunu ortaya koyuyor</i> ”. (erkek 18-25)	The quality of being pleasing to the senses or to the mind. A pleasing feature.
“ <i>Almışken en kaliteli olanını, en iş görür olanını ve en güzelini almak isterim</i> ”. (kadin 18-25)	The quality of being pleasing to the senses or to the mind. A pleasing feature.
“ <i>Normalde bir buzdolabı alınırken no frost veya A sınıfı enerji gibi özelliklere bılırken artık teknolojinin de ilerlemesiyle reklamlarla da gördüğümüz gibi birçok güzel özellik bizlere sunulmuştur</i> ”. (erkek 18-25)	The quality of being pleasing to the senses or to the mind. A pleasing feature.

Wife:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*wife*” as:

- 1- the woman that a man is married to

In the responses the word “*wife*” has been used in a context which parallel definition 1

For example the statement “*Today man of the house share the house work with his wife*” (man 18-25). As another example “*We can see that men relatively help to their spouses in kitchen chores*” (woman 18-25).

Table 12. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (wife)

<i>Bugün evin erkeği de ev işlerini hanımı ile paylaşmaktadır. (erkek 18-25)</i>	the woman that a man is married to
<i>Erkeğin ise mutfak işlerinde biraz olsun eşine yardım ettiğini görüyoruz. (kadın 18-25)</i>	the woman that a man is married to

Passive:

In the responses the word “passive” has not been used in a context.

Business women:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*business women*” as:

- 1- A person who works in business, especially at a high level.
- 2- A person who is skilful in business and financial matters.

In the responses the word “*business women*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*There is no longer a fierce line between men and women in such commercials compared with the past. Women no longer only deal with the house chores. They also part of many commercials regarding various occupations (e.g construction commercials). Because women also work. So they are both housewives and businesswomen*” (woman 18-25). As another example “*In the commercials, we can see that women now strong and successful as a businesswoman as well*” (man 18-25). Furthermore “*Now just like Nil Karabrahimgil says in her song, women can make children and career. So they are now businesswomen*” (woman 18-25).

Table 13. Discourse Analysis of Code Femininity (business women)

<p><i>“Bu gibi reklamlarda kadın ve erkek arasında geçmişe nazaran sert bir çizgi bulunmamaktadır. Kadın sadece ev işleriyle ilgili bir rol üstlenmiyor. Aynı zamanda birçok meslek gruplarıyla ilgili reklamlarda (örneğin, inşaat reklamı gibi) rol almaktadır. Çünkü kadında artık çalışıyor, yani hem ev hanımı hem iş kadını. (kadın 18-25)</i></p>	<p>A person who works in business, especially at a high level.</p>
<p><i>“İzlediğimiz reklamlarda kadının da artık iş kadını olarak güçlü ve başarılı bir şekilde yer aldığını görmekteyiz”. (erkek 18-25)</i></p>	<p>A person who works in business, especially at a high level.</p>
<p><i>“Günümüz koşullarında Nil Karaibrahimgil şarkısında da söylediği gibi, kadınlar çocuk da yapar, kariyer de. Yani onlar da artık iş kadını”. (kadın 18-25)</i></p>	<p>A person who works in business, especially at a high level.</p>

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed third frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 1 (masculinity) (which contains the words provider, man, father, husband, macho, businessman, strength). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Provider:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*provider*” as:

- 1- A person or an organization that supplies sb with sth they need or want.

In the responses the word “*provider*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*While there used to be no father figure shown in a fridge commercial or emphasized from the financial aspect, now they have the role of helping mother role and taking*

responsibilities at home” (woman 40 +). As another example *“It goes beyond the clichés. At the end of the day, woman is a person who always does the house work, be the housewife while man does not help his wife and just sit at home in reality”* (man 40 +). Moreover *“The mother firstly thinks about the health of her child and delivers this to the father. Since the father covers the finances, he approves the purchase of product. Yet it seems that only mother cares about her child, the father also cares about the health of his child as well”* (man 18-25). As another example *“The fridge commercial of Beko appeals to both women and men. It infuses to the women that she can store all food she want for a long time while men will not exceed their budget”* (man 18-25). In addition *“Father has role of person working and bringing money”* (man 40 +).

Table 14. Discourse Analysis of Code Masculinity (provider)

<i>“Eskiden bir buzdolabı reklamı için baba rolü etrafta gözükmek veya sadece maddi yönden vurgulanırken günümüz reklamlarında anne rolüne daha yardım eden ve evdeki sorumlulukları üstlenen bir role bürünmüştür”. (kadin 40 +)</i>	A person or an organization that supplies sb with sth they need or want.
<i>“Kalıplaşmış kuralların dışına çıkmış. Sonuçta kadın gerçek hayatta her zaman sürekli iş yapan erkek ise eşine maddi açıdan bu beyaz eşyaları sağlayan, eşine yardım etmeyen, evde oturan bir kişidir”. (erkek 40 +)</i>	A person or an organization that supplies sb with sth they need or want.
<i>“Anne çocuğunun en başta sağlığını düşünür bunu babaya iletir ve maddi kısmı karşılayacak olan baba olduğu için o da bu ürünün alınmasını onaylar. Çünkü ne kadar çocuk yetiştirilirken sadece anne ilgileniyor gibi gözükse de baba içinde çocuğun sağlığı önemlidir”. (erkek 18-25)</i>	A person or an organization that supplies sb with sth they need or want.
<i>“Bekonun buzdolabı reklamı ise aslında hem kadına hem de erkeğe hitap eder. Kadını istediği her türlü yiyeceği uzun süre koruyabileceği, erkeğin ise bu sebepten bütçesini aşamayacağını benimsetiyor”. (erkek 18-25)</i>	A person or an organization that supplies sb with sth they need or want.
<i>“Baba çalışıp eve para getiren kişi rolünü üstlenmiştir”. (erkek 40 +)</i>	A person or an organization that supplies sb with sth they need or want.

Men:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*men*” as:

- 1- An adult male human.
- 2- Humans as a group or from a particular period of history.
- 3- A person, either male or female.
- 4- A man who comes from the place mentioned or whose job or interest is connected with the thing mentioned: businessman, sportman.
- 5- A man who likes or who does the thing mentioned: a betting, drinking.
- 6- A man who works for or supports a particular organization, comes from a particular town.
- 7- A man who comes to your house to do a job.
- 8- Used for addressing a male person in an angry or impatient way.
- 9- Used for addressing a male person.

In the responses the word “man” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1 and 9. For example the statement “*Although I don’t see anything close to Turkish people, I can speak for 2013 and beyond that men have started to let loose a little bit more and give more importance to help their wives at home*” (woman 40 +). Moreover “*Men now also work on house chores*” (woman 18-25). As another statement “*Fridge also appeals to both women and men. It infuses into women that they can store all food they want for a long time, therefore men will not exceed their budget*” (woman 40 +).

Table 15. Discourse Analysis of Code Masculinity (men)

“Erkekleri temsilen reklamlarda Türklere pek yakın bir yön göremememe rağmen 2013 ve ilerisi için söyleyebilirim ki; erkekler biraz daha yumuşamaya ev işlerinde yardım etmeye eşlerine daha çok özen göstermeye başlıyor”. (kadin 40+)	An adult male human. Used for addressing a male person.
“Erkeklerde artık ev işlerinde görünmeye başladılar”. (kadin 18-25)	An adult male human. Used for addressing a male person.
“Buzdolabı ise aslında hem kadına hem de erkeğe hitap eder. Kadını istediği her türlü yiyeceği uzun süre koruyabileceği, erkeğin ise bu sebepten bütçesini aşamayacağını benimsetiyor”. (kadin 40 +)	An adult male human. Used for addressing a male person.

Father:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*father*” as:

- 1- A male parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as the father to a child.
- 2- A person’s ANCESTORS (= people who are related to you who lived in the past).
- 3- The first man to introduce a new way of thinking about sth or of doing sth.
- 4- Used by Christians to refer to God.
- 5- The title of a priest, especially in the Roman Catholic Church and Orthodox Church.

In the responses the word “*father*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*The reason why the child gets angry to his father is that men are not really good at these duties, thus make mistakes, but when women come and do laundry at 30 degrees, it is right since they know the work*” (woman 40 +). As another example “*For example; it was very rare to see a father putting clothes into washing machine or doing any house chore in the old commercials, but now we see such incidents more frequently*” (woman 18-25). Moreover “*Everything is clear, accurate including mothers and fathers and in two commercials (fridge) there is a mother and father cooperation. in other two commercials, only mother and her baby are seen. The only expectation of baby is to be with the mother and spend time with her*” (man 40 +)...

Table 16. Discourse Analysis of Code Masculinity (father)

<p>“Çocuğun çamaşır makinası kısmında babasına kızması 30 derecede yıkandığı için bunun nedeni ise erkeklerin bu konular hakkında iyi olmadıkları bu yüzden yanlış yaptığını söyler ama kadın geip 30 derecede yapınca doğru olduğunu anlar neden çünkü kadın zaten bu konulara hakim”. (kadın 40+)</p>	<p>A male parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as the father to a child.</p>
<p>“Örneğin; eski reklamlarda evdeki babanın çamaşır makinesine çamaşır koyması veya herhangi bir ev işiyle ilgileniyor olarak görmek çok zorken artık günümüz reklamlarında bu tarz görüntülere çok daha sık bir şekilde rastlanmaktadır”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>A male parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as the father to a child.</p>
<p>“Anneler ve babalar dahil herşey temiz, düzgün, tertipli ve iki reklamda (buzdolabı) anne ve baba işbirliği var. Diğer iki reklamda görünürde sadece anne ve bebeği. Bebeğin tek beklentisi anne ile beraber olup vakit geçirmek”... (erkek 40+)</p>	<p>A male parent of a child or animal; a person who is acting as the father to a child.</p>

Husband:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “husband” as:

- 1- The man that a women is married to; a married man.

In the responses the word “husband” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “Men now also work on house chores. There is no longer only women for tidying up the cabinets, doing the laundry. The functionality and practicality in using the products are emphasized for both men and women” (woman 18-25).

Table 17. Discourse Analysis of Code Masculinity (husband)

<p>“Eşlerde artık ev işlerinde görünmeye başladılar. Mutfakta dolabı yerleştirirken, çamaşırı yıkarken sadece kadın temsili ortada olmaktan çıkmıştır. Ürünlerin kullanımının hem erkekler için hem de kadınlar için ne kadar kullanışlı ve pratik olduğu vurgulanmıştır”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>The man that a women is married to; a married man.</p>
--	---

Macho:

In the responses the word “*macho*” has not been used in a context.

Business man:

In the responses the word “*business man*” has not been used in a context.

Strength:

In the responses the word “*strenght*” has not been used in a context.

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed ranking fourth frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 3 (society change) (which contains the words culture, community, old generation, difference, new generation, change, social, technology). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Culture:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*culture*” as:

- 1- The customs and beliefs, art, way of life and social organization of a particular country or group.
- 2- A country, group, etc. with its own beliefs, etc.
- 3- Art, music, literature, etc, thought of as a group.
- 4- The beliefs and attitudes about sth that people in a particular group or organization share.
- 5- The growing of plants or breeding of particular animals in order to get a particular substance or crop from them.

In the responses the word “*culture*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. and 2. For example the statement “*The child is generally a boy. This is an example coming from Turkish family culture. The older child must be potentially a boy while younger child must be a girl. I can first see that. The child is the first child and it’s a boy. The discourse is made only through the child just to make it nice*” (woman 40 +). As another example “*We can understand that women give much importance on cleaning and kitchen chores by the Turkish culture*” (man 18-25). Moreover “*In Turkish culture, the mother namely woman is the person generally doing*

all work correctly even in the eye of a child.... I think it emphasized the position of woman in Turkish society” (man 40 +)... In addition “Each society give a role to woman and man from the cultural aspect” (woman 18-25).

Table 18. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (culture)

<p><i>“Genel olarak çocuk aynı hep erkek çocuktur. Bu da türk aile kültür yapısında olması arzulan bir örnektir. Büyük çocuk potansiyel olarak her zaman erkek çocuk olmak zorundadır, küçük çocukta kız olmak zorundadır. Burada da ilk onu görüyorum. İlk çocuk ve erkek çocuktur ve söylemlerde sadece çocuk üzerinden konumlandırılmıştır. Sevimli hale getirilmesi için”. (kadin 40 +)</i></p>	<p>The customs and beliefs, art, way of life and social organization of a particular country or group. A country, group, etc. with its own beliefs, etc.</p>
<p><i>“Türk kültürünün yapısı gereği kadının temizliğe ve mutfak işine çok önem verdiğini anlıyoruz.” (erkek 18-25)</i></p>	<p>The customs and beliefs, art, way of life and social organization of a particular country or group. A country, group, etc. with its own beliefs, etc.</p>
<p><i>“Türk kültüründe bu işleri genelde yapan ve doğru olarak yapan kişi küçük çocuğa göre bile annedir yani kadındır.... Kadının Türk toplumundaki yerini vurgulamışlar bence”... (erkek 40 +)</i></p>	<p>The customs and beliefs, art, way of life and social organization of a particular country or group. A country, group, etc. with its own beliefs, etc.</p>
<p><i>“Her toplum kültürel olarak kadın ve erkeğe bir rol biçer”. (kadin 18-25)</i></p>	<p>The customs and beliefs, art, way of life and social organization of a particular country or group. A country, group, etc. with its own beliefs, etc.</p>

Community:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “community” as:

- 1- All the people who live in a particular area, country, etc. when talked about as a group.
- 2- A group of people who share the same religion, race, job, etc.
- 3- The feeling of sharing things and belonging to a group in the place where you live.
- 4- A group of plants and animals growing or living in the same place or environment.

In the responses the word “community” has been used in a context which parallels definition 3. For example the statement “*Not only for this commercial but also for all white goods commercial, the woman figure is used as the person spending the longest time in the kitchen since kitchen and woman is accepted as a whole in Turkish society*” (man 40 +).. As another example “*The mother namely woman is the person who does such duties correctly even for a little child...I think they emphasized the position of woman in society...But I believe they have missed out that many women work now*” (woman 18-25)... Moreover “*The duties and responsibilities given to women and men have begun to change in our culture and society*” (woman 18-25) . In addition “*In any case, I have never seen a man washing the dishes, grumbling as ‘huff and puff’, complaining about the dirt in any commercial. The reason of this is that men don’t wash the dishes in reality and they are not used in commercials to be convincing. Men have not work on such chores yet, but they will in the end and we will see it in commercials*” (woman 18-25). As another example “*I think the sales of product ‘BEKO’ have increased because Turkish society is keen on memory and child and if the commercial is attractive then the demand increases*” (man 18-25).

Table 19. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (community)

<p>“Sadece bu reklam için değil tüm beyaz eşya reklamlarında mutfakta en çok vakit geçiren kadın figürü kullanılır. Çünkü mutfak ve kadın Türk toplumunda bir bütün olarak kabul edilir”. (erkek 40 +)</p>	<p>The feeling of sharing things and belonging to a group in the place where you live.</p>
<p>“Bu tarz işleri genelde yapan ve doğru olarak yapan kişi küçük çocuğa göre bile annedir yani kadındır.... Kadının Türk toplumundaki yerini vurgulamışlar bence... Ama artık çoğu kadının da çalıştığını atlamışlar diye düşünüyorum”... (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>The feeling of sharing things and belonging to a group in the place where you live.</p>
<p>“Kadın ve erkeğe yüklenen görevler ve temsiliyetler bizim kültürümüzde ve toplumumuzda da artık değişmeye başlamıştır”. (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>The feeling of sharing things and belonging to a group in the place where you live.</p>
<p>“Zaten şu ana kadar gösterilen reklamlarda hiçbir zaman bir erkeğin bulaşıkla uğraştığı ‘uff’layıp ‘puff’ladığı kirler hakkında isyan etmesini görmedim. Bunun nedeni ise hem gerçekte erkeğin bulaşıkla ilgilenmemesi hemde reklamın inandırıcılık açısından erkeğin oynatılmaması, çünkü yaşadığımız toplumda henüz erkek bu denli ev işlerinde yer almamaktadır ama gün gelecek ve alacaktır ve biz bunu reklamlarda da göreceğiz”. (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>The feeling of sharing things and belonging to a group in the place where you live.</p>
<p>“Türk toplumundaki bellek ve çocuk düşkünlüğü sayesinde bence ‘BEKO’ adlı ürünün satışları artmıştır. Çünkü çekici bir reklam yaparak o ürüne olan talep artar”. (erkek 18-25)</p>	<p>The feeling of sharing things and belonging to a group in the place where you live.</p>

Old Generation:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “old generation” as:

- 1- All the people who were born at about the same time.
- 2- The average time in which children grow up, became adults and have children with their own (usually considered to be about 30 years).
- 3- A single stage in the history of a family.

- 4- A group of people of similar age involved in a particular activity.
- 5- A stage in the development of a product, usually a technical one.

In the responses the word “*old generation*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*Beko has created its products as robots used them to narrate that we used to wash our products under very high temperatures or there is no need to scrap the oven to clean it after cooking*” (woman 40 +). As another example “*For example; it was very rare to see a father putting clothes into washing machine or doing any house chore in the old commercials, but now we see such incidents more frequently*” (man 18-25). Moreover “*While there is a woman looking after her home, cooking, nursing her child, man is dealing with the laundry and looking after his child when compared with the past. He has a role that helps the woman. In old commercials, women were alone, now we can see that men help their spouses which shows that men are becoming more domestic people*” (woman 18-25). In addition “*Another aspect is that 50 years ago, mothers were doing their house chores under very difficult conditions; doing laundry by using stones, washing their dishes by their hands; however today a woman can do all these chores at the same time and even allocate some time for herself too. It was impossible to watch such commercials in the past*” (woman 40 +). As another statement “*I can observe in the commercial that 20 years ago, dishes and laundry are washed by hand and they don’t allocate any time for themselves. It is narrated that with the developments in technology, life becomes easier and especially women can spend some time for themselves*” (woman 18-25).

Table 20. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (old generation)

<p>“Eskiden bizler eşyalarımızı ürünlerimizi çok yüksek sıcaklıkta yıkarken ya da fırında yemek yaptıktan sonra pişirilen fırını temizlemek için fırını kazımaya gerek olmadığını resmen beko ürünlerini robotlaştırarak betimlemiş”. (kadın 40 +)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>
<p>“Örneğin; eski reklamlarda evdeki babanın çamaşır makinesine çamaşır koyması veya herhangi bir ev işiyle ilgileniyor olarak görmek çok zorken artık günümüz reklamlarında bu tarz görüntülere çok daha sık bir şekilde rastlanmaktadır”. (erkek 18-25)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>
<p>“Eviyle ilgili, yemeğini yapan çocuğuyla ilgilenen bir kadın varken erkek ise eskilere göre çamaşırıyla ilgilenen evinde çocuğuyla ilgilenen bir konumdadır. Kadına yardımcı olan bir rol üstlenmiştir. Eski reklamlarda kadını tek görürken artık erkeğin eşine yardım etmesi destek olması gibi reklamlar söz konusudur. Buda günden güne erkeğin daha evcimen olduğunu gösterir”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>
<p>“Diğer bir bakış açısı da bundan 50 yıl öncesine kadar anneler evlerinin işini çok zor şartlarda yapabiliyordu, çamaşırı taşla vurarak, bulaşığı elde yıkıyordu, bugün ise bir kadın evde tüm bu işleri hem aynı anda yapabiliyor, bununla birlikte çocuğuna bakıp, kendine de zaman bile ayırabiliyor. Eskiden bizlerin bu tarz reklamlar izlemeleri imkansızdı”. (kadın 40 +)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>
<p>“ Reklamda 20 yıl önce bulaşıkların çamaşırın elde yıkandığını kadınların kendilerine hiç zaman ayırmadıklarını özellikle annelerin iş yaptığını görmekteydim. Teknolojinin de gelişmesiyle birlikte hayatın kolaylaştırıldığını ve özellikle annelerin kendilerine zaman ayırdığını anlatmaktadır”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>

Difference:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*difference*” as:

- 1- The way in which two people or things are not like eachother; the way in which sb/sth has changed.
- 2- The amount that sth is greater or smaller than sth else.
- 3- A disasreement between people.

In the responses the word “*difference*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*Although we see change and difference in some issues, we can always see commercials that mother always represents the house*” (man 18-25).

Table 21. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (difference)

“Günümüzde bazı konularda değişim ve farklılık görüyor olsak da annenin her zaman evi temsil ettiğini reklamlarda görebiliyoruz”. (erkek 18-25)	The way in which two people or things are not like eachother; the way in which sb/sth has changed.
---	--

New Generation:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*new generation*” as:

- 1- All the people who were born at about the same time.
- 2- The average time in which children grow up, became adults and have children with their own (usually considered to be about 30 years).
- 3- A single stage in the history of a family.
- 4- A group of people of similar age involved in a particular activity.
- 5- A stage in the development of a product, usually a techinal one.

In the responses the word “*new generation*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*It goes beyond the clichés. At the end of the day, woman is a person who always does the house work, be the housewife while man does not help his wife and just sit at home in reality. But since the new generation grows up responsibly and literate, clichés are no longer available which is a very good thing. We can clearly see this in Beko’s commercials*” (woman 18-25). As another example “*We, young people as the new generation, live what we see in commercials. Man cooks in the kitchen, does shopping, does laundry if needed. Our grandfathers and fathers are not used to do such duties but now they do it as well since commercials divert them as well*” (man 18-25). In addition “*We, new generation, are much more aware now, support ourselves, because we get education. Therefore; woman and man are equal. But our mothers’ lives were not like our lives, now they have the same lives as well because we see the same commercials and consume the same things*” (woman 18-25).

Table 22. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (new generation)

<p>“<i>Kalıplaşmış kuralların dışına çıkmış.Sonuçta kadın gerçek hayatta her zaman sürekli iş yapan erkek ise eşine yardım etmeyen,oturan bir kişidir. Ama şimdi yeni nesil bilinçli ve eğitilmiş yetiştiği için bu kalıplaşmış kuralların dışına çıkmıştır iyide olmuştur. Bunuda Bekonun bu reklamların görüyoruz</i>”. (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>
<p>“<i>Yeni bir nesil olan biz gençler reklamlarda gördüğümüzü yaşıyoruz artık. Erkek mutfakta yemek de yapıyor, alışverişte yapıyor, gerekirse çamaşır da kuruyor. Fakat eskiden dedelerimiz ve babalarımız bunları yapmıyordu fakat şimdi onlarda yapıyor. Çünkü reklamlar onları şekillendiriyor</i>”. (erkek 18-25)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>
<p>“<i>Yeni nesil yani bizler artık daha bilinçliyiz, kendi ayaklarımız üzerinde durabiliyoruz, çünkü eğitimliyiz. O yüzden kadın ve erkek eşit duruma gelmiş durumda. Ama eskiden annelerimizin hayatı bizimki gibi değildi ama şimdi onlarında öyle. Çünkü aynı reklamları görüyor ve tüketiyor</i>”. (kadin 18-25)</p>	<p>All the people who were born at about the same time.</p>

--	--

Change:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*change*” as:

- 1- To become different.
- 2- To make sb\sth different.
- 3- To pass or make sb\sth pass from one state or form into another.
- 4- To stop having one state, position or direction and start having another.
- 5- To replace one thing, person, service etc. with sth new or different.
- 6- To exchange positions, place, etc. with sb else, so that you have what they have, and they have what you have.

In the responses the word “*change*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*The impact of changing technology on our lives and food is clearly described in Beko commercial*” (man 18-25). As another example “*A happy, aspiring family picture and simplicity of electrical tools that can be used by almost everybody with the changing and developing technology are emphasized*” (woman 18-25). In addition “*It is shown that it will facilitate the daily lives of people with the developed and changed product features*” (woman 18-25). Moreover “*Also, since it gives the message that everything can be done in a much practical, easy and quick way due to the changing and developing technology, it covers all the things that a consumer wants*” (man 18-25).

Table 23. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (change)

“Değişen teknolojinin hayatımızda ve yiyeceklerimizde etkisini Beko reklamında çok açık bir şekilde anlatmaktadır”. (erkek 18-25)	To become different.
“Mutlu, özenilecek bir aile tablosu ile gelişen ve değişen teknoloji ile elektrikli aletlerin neredeyse hemen hemen herkes tarafından kullanılabilir olacak şekilde kolaylıkta oluşu vurgulanmaktadır”. (kadın 18-25)	To become different.
“Geliştirdiği ve değiştirdiği ürün özellikleriyle insanların günlük hayatlarında yaşamlarını kolaylaştıracak olacağı gösterilmektedir”. (kadın 18-25)	To become different.
“Ayrıca ürünlerin gelişen ve değişen teknolojisi ile birlikte daha pratik ve kolay, aynı zamanda hızlı bir şekilde yapılabileceği mesajı verdiği için tüketicinin aradığı bütün özelliklere cevap vermektedir”. (erkek 18-25)	To become different.

Social:

In the responses the word “*social*” has not been used in a context.

Technology:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*technology*” as:

- 1- Scientific knowledge used in practical ways in industry.
- 2- Machinery or equipment designed using technology.

In the responses the word “*technology*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*It describes that life has become easier and especially mothers have started to allocate time for themselves with the developments in technology*” (man 40 +). As

another example *“The latest products introduced by Beko with their state of art status shorten the time for house chores, clean and put up everything confidently”* (woman 40 +). Moreover *“These commercials interpret the evolution of modern life style. It shows how such advanced technology is modernized and mankind has changed”* (woman 40 +). Furthermore *“Normally the features of no frost or A class were been looked for when a fridge was purchased; now many features are introduced to us as we see in commercials with the development of technology. For example; when buying, we now look for the cleaning feature of an oven instead of cooking feature. We prefer products that can store vegetable and fruits longer. We want to save time, get tired less since nowadays the conditions and commercials present us these products. We want to make our lives much easier”* (woman 18-25). In addition *“We think that the products shown in commercials are the best since they follow the technology and we feel the need to buy them. As much as we buy these products, we fulfill our purchasing need”* (woman 18-25).

Table 24. Discourse Analysis of Code Society Change (technology)

<i>“Teknolojinin gelişmesiyle birlikte hayatın kolaylaştırdığını ve özellikle annelerin kendilerine zaman ayırdığını anlatmaktadır”. (erkek 40 +)</i>	Scientific knowledge used in practical ways in industry.
<i>“Beko'nun son çıkardığı ürünlerinin son teknolojik uyum içinde evdeki işlerini daha da kısaltmakta ve güven içinde eşyaların temizlemekte ve kaldırmaktadır”. (kadın 40 +)</i>	Scientific knowledge used in practical ways in industry.
<i>“Bu reklamlar modern yaşam tarzının geldiği noktayı yorumlamaktadır. Bu tarz ileri teknolojinin nedenli çağ atladığını geçmişe bir göz atarsak insanoğlunun nerden nereye geldiğini gözler önüne sergilemiş oluyor”. (kadın 40 +)</i>	Scientific knowledge used in practical ways in industry.
<i>“Normalde bir buzdolabı alınırken no frost veya A sınıfı enerji gibi özelliklere bılırken artık teknolojinin de ilerlemesiyle reklamlarla da gördüğümüz gibi birçok güzel özellik bizlere sunulmuş. Örneğin bir fırın alırken sadece yemek pişirme özelliği değil de temizlenme özelliğine de bakar duruma geldik. Sebzeyi meyveyi daha uzun ömürlü tutan ürünleri tercih ediyoruz. Zamandan tasarruf etmek istiyoruz, daha az</i>	Scientific knowledge used in practical ways in industry.

yorulmak istiyoruz. Çünkü günümüz şartları ve reklamları bize bu ürünleri sunuyor. Hayatımızı daha da kolaylaştırmak istiyoruz". (kadin 18-25)	
"Reklamlarda anlatılan ürünler genelde teknolojiyi takip ettiği için en iyiler olduğunu düşünüyoruz ve o ürünü satın alma ihtiyacı duyarız. Bu ürünleri aldıkça da satın alma ihtiyacımızı karşılamış oluruz". (kadin 18-25)	Scientific knowledge used in practical ways in industry.

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed ranking fifth frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 4 (representation) (which contains the words image, belief, only, attractiveness, representation reflect, shaping). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Image:

In the responses the word "*image*" has not been used in a context.

Belief:

In the responses the word "*belief*" has not been used in a context.

Only:

In the responses the word "*only*" has not been used in a context.

Attractiveness:

In the responses the word "*attractiveness*" has not been used in a context.

Representation Reflect:

Oxford dictionary defines the word "*representation*" as:

- 1- The act of presenting sb\sth in a particular way; something that shows or describes sth.

- 2- The fact of having representatives who will speak or vote for you or on your behalf.
- 3- Formal statements made to sb in authority, especially in order to make your opinions known or to protest.

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*reflect*” as:

- 1- To show the image of sb\sth on the surface os sth such as a mirror, water or glass.
- 2- To throw back light, heat, sound, etc. from a surface.
- 3- To show or be a sign of the nature of sth or of sb`s attitude or feeling.
- 4- To think carefully and deeply about sth.

In the responses the word “*representation reflect*” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “*The reflection of only woman representation while tidying the cupboards in the kitchen, doing the laundry is eliminated*” (man 18-25). As another example “*The reflection of man representation in commercials are not separate and unrelated from white goods. The reflection of father representation at home is a person who helps his wife, putting things into the fridge*” (man 40 +). Furthermore “*In 4 commercials that I watched, both woman and man are represented with a role that reflects the kindness of sharing which should be found in people and available in the inner world of each individual although they may not show*” (woman 18-25). Moreover “*As for gender representation, woman represents her own gender. There is still a woman taking care of her home, cooking, caring her child, man is doing the laundry and caring his child when compared with the past. He has a role helping the woman*” (woman 18-25). As another statement “*In the reflection of woman and man gender representation; the aim is to show that all house chores are no longer only for the women or they are not something that can be done only by women; a man can also perform the same duty or responsibilities*” (man 18-25).

Table 25. Discourse Analysis of Code Representation (representation/reflect)

<p>“Mutfakta dolabı yerleştirirken, çamaşırları yıkarken sadece kadın temsilinin yansımaları ortada olmaktan çıkmıştır”. (kadın 40 +)</p>	<p>The act of presenting sb\sth in a particular way; something that shows or describes sth.</p>
<p>“Reklamlardaki erkek temsilinin yansıması evde kullanılan beyaz eşyalardan bağımsız ve alakasız gösterilmemektedir. Evde ki baba temsili yansıması eşine yardım eden, buzdolabına eşyaları yerleştiren bir kişidir”. (erkek 40 +)</p>	<p>The act of presenting sb\sth in a particular way; something that shows or describes sth.</p>
<p>“İzlediğim 4 reklam filminde de kadında ve erkekte aslında olması gereken ve her bireyin gerçekleştiremeye de iç dünyasında yer alan hayatın onarıcı unsuru olan paylaşım güzelliğini yansıtan bir rolle temsil edilmişlerdir”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>The act of presenting sb\sth in a particular way; something that shows or describes sth.</p>
<p>“Cinsiyet temsilciliği olarak kadın kendi cinsiyetini temsil etmektedir. Yine eviyle ilgili, yemeğini yapan çocuğuyla ilgilenen bir kadın varken erkek ise eskilere göre çamaşırıyla ilgilenen evinde çocuğuyla ilgilenen bir konumdadır. Kadına yardımcı olan bir rol üstlenmiştir”. (kadın 18-25)</p>	<p>The act of presenting sb\sth in a particular way; something that shows or describes sth.</p>
<p>“Bayan ve erkek cinsiyet temsilinin yansımasında; reklam kendi ürünleriyle artık tüm ev işlerinin sadece bayanlara yönelik ya da sadece bayanların yapacağı şeyler olarak değil; bir erkeğinde aynı görev veya sorumluluklarda görev alabileceği gösterilmek istenmiştir”. (erkek 18-25)</p>	<p>The act of presenting sb\sth in a particular way; something that shows or describes sth.</p>

Shape:

In the responses the word “*shape*” has not been used in a context.

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed ranking sixth frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 5 (roles) (which contains the words gender roles, men's roles, women's roles, head/leader/authority). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Gender Roles:

Oxford dictionary defines the word "*gender*" as:

- 1- the fact of being male or female
- 2- the system in some languages of dividing nouns, adjectives, and pronouns into masculine, feminine or neuter.

Oxford dictionary defines the word "*role*" as:

- 1- the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation
- 2- a character in a play or film

In the responses the word "gender roles" has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement "From the woman and man gender representation, the advertisement tried to deliver through their products that all housework are not only for women or works that can only be done by women; a man can also take part in the same works or gender roles. For example; while it was too difficult to see a father doing laundry or handling any housework, such cases are encountered more in today's advertisements (Female 18-25)". As another example, "As for gender representation, woman represents her own gender. She cooks, takes care of her child while man is at the position of doing laundry, taking care of children when compared with the past. Man has undertaken a gender role that helps to woman. While woman was shown by herself in the old advertisements, now there are adverts reflecting the man should help and support his wife. This shows that man has become more domestic day by day (Female 18-25)". Moreover "It has a significant role in the determination of roles since as a woman but especially a woman who wants to study in university and build a career, I may not allocate too much time for laundry, washing the dishes, cooking, cleaning when I start working. These advertisements aim to use more hygienic products in shorter time, store food longer, thus they deliver attractive subjects for woman. Due to the advertisements like Beko, we may adopt to use the products that

are beneficial for us, children, family as a principle for our future. The advertisements of white goods are mostly the helper of woman. Featuring a child figure in advertisements ensures that motherhood instinct will arise and positive decisions will be made accordingly. I find such advertisements as beneficial and important for the determination of gender roles (female 18-25). In addition “It has a role in the identification of gender roles since there was no father role shown for a refrigerator advertisement or emphasized from the financial aspect in the past, now his role covers helping the mother role and undertaking household responsibilities. Although they may not address to all groups, woman are influenced and affected for their future roles since such advertisements appeal to the needs of almost every person (female 18-25)”. As another statement “I think these advertisements have a crucial role on the identification of gender roles. People are significantly affected from all aspects including negative aspects. Advertisements lead the lives of people, societies all over (Male 18-25)”.

Table 26. Discourse Analysis of Code Representation (gender roles)

<p><i>“Bayan ve erkek cinsiyet temsilinde; reklam kendi ürünleriyle artık tüm ev işlerinin sadece bayanlara yönelik ya da sadece bayanların yapacağı şeyler olarak değil; bir erkeğinde aynı görev veya cinsiyet rollerinde görev alabileceği gösterilmek istenmiştir. Örneğin; eski reklamlarda evdeki babanın çamaşır makinesine çamaşır koyması veya herhangi bir ev işiyle ilgileniyor olarak görmek çok zorken artık günümüz reklamlarında bu tarz görüntülere çok daha sık bir şekilde rastlanmaktadır (kadın18-25)”.</i></p>	<p>the fact of being male or female the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>
<p><i>“Cinsiyet temsilyeti olarak kadın kendi cinsiyetini temsil etmektedir. Yine eviyle ilgili, yemeğini yapan çocuğuyla ilgilenen bir kadın varken erkek ise eskilere göre çamaşırarıya ilgilenen evinde çocuğuyla ilgilenen bir konumdadır. Erkek kadına yardımcı olan bir cinsiyet rolü üstlenmiştir. Eski reklamlarda kadını tek görürükten artık erkeğin eşine yardım etmesi destek</i></p>	<p>the fact of being male or female the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>

<p><i>olmsdı gibi reklamlar söz konusudur. Buda günden güne erkeğin daha evcimen olduğunu gösterir (kadın 18-25)”.</i></p>	
<p><i>“Rollerin belirlenmesinde önemli rol oynar. Çünkü bir bayan olarak ve üniversite okuyup kariyer kariyer yapmayı hedefleyen bir bayan olarak iş edindiğimde çamaşır, bulaşık, yemek, temizlik gibi konulara çok fazla vakit ayıramayabilirim. Bu reklamlar daha kısa sürede daha hijyenik ürünler kullanmayı, daha uzun sürede yiyecek korumayı hedefleyip kadına cazip konular işliyor. Geleceğimizi düşünüp kendimize, çocuğumuza, ailemize yararlı, bizim avantajımızı sağlayan ürünler kullanmayı ilke edinebiliyoruz beko gibi reklamlarla. Beyaz eşya reklamları daha çok kadının yardımcısı, kadının elinden tutan reklamlardır. Çocuk figürünün reklamda oynatılması ise yine annelik içgüdüsünün ortaya çıkıp bu yönde olumlu karar verilmesini sağlar. Bu tür reklamları cinsiyet rollerinin belirlenmesi için yararlı ve önemli buluyorum (kadın 18-25)</i></p>	<p>the fact of being male or female the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>
<p><i>“Cinsiyet rollerinin tanımlanmasında rol oynar. Çünkü eskiden bir buzdolabı reklamı için baba rolü etrafta gözükmezken veya sadece maddi yönden vurgulanırken günümüz reklamlarında anne rolüne daha yardım eden ve evdeki sorumlulukları üstlenen bir role bürünmüştür. Aynı zamanda her kitleye hitap etmese de bu tarz reklamlar hemen her insanın ihtiyaçlarına seslendiği için bayanlarında etkilenecek ilerde bürünecekleri rollerde etkili olmaktadır (kadın 18-25)”.</i></p>	<p>the fact of being male or female the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>
<p><i>“Bence bu reklamlar cinsiyet rollerinin tanımlanmasında çok büyük hayati bir rol oynar. İnsanlar her yönden çok etkilenirler olumsuz yönlerden etkilerler.Reklamlar her yönden insanların toplumların hayatlarına yön verirler (erkek 18-25)”..</i></p>	<p>the fact of being male or female the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>

Men's Roles:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*man*” as:

- 1- an adult male person

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*role*” as:

- 1-the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation
- 2- a character in a play or film

In the responses the word “men`s roles” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “Let`s go back to the white goods advertisements of the past, woman were taking the clean clothes, hanging them up and drying them out or doing grocery shopping, putting them into the cupboards, washing the dishes, wiping them, cooking the food, serving etc. So all housework were woman`s responsibility, however there is an equality and work sharing in today`s advertisements caused by the changing mentality. Such advertisements are good for the people who will start a family since it shows that there is a gradual change in the role of man (male 18-25). Another example, “The advertisements that we are watching show that especially the roles of man are changed or may change due to the changing and developing technology (female 18-25)”. Moreover “When I think back about old advertisements, the roles of man and woman were not represented in this way. The help of man to woman was not even thought in our time, but now everything is way too different (female 40 +)”.

Table 27. Discourse Analysis of Code Representation (men`s roles)

<p><i>“Geçmişteki beyaz eşya reklamlarına gidelim bir çamaşır makinası reklamı bayan yıkadığı çamaşırları alır serer ve kurutur yada ev alışverişini alır, yerleştirir, bulaşıkları yıkar kurutur yemeği pişiri, sunar v.b. Yani bakıldığında ev işleri hep kadının üzerindeyken günümüzdeki reklamlarda bir eşitlik görev paylaşımı mevcut buda zamanla değişen düşünce yapısından kaynaklanır. Bu tarz reklamlar yuva kuracaklar için iyi bir örnektir. Cunku erkeğin rolunun yavaş yavaş değişmeye başladığını gösterir</i></p>	<p><i>an adult male person</i></p> <p><i>the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</i></p>
--	---

<i>(erkek 18-25)”. “İzlemis olduğumuz reklamlar günden güne değişen ve gelişen teknoloji ile özellikle erkeklerin rollerinin değiştiğini veya değişebileceğini gösterir” (kadın 18-25.</i>	<i>an adult male person the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</i>
<i>“Gecmiş reklamlar aklıma geldikçe erkeğin veya kadının roller hiç bu şekilde temsil edilmiyordu. Bizim zamanımızda erkeğin biz kadınlara yardım etmesi söz konusu bile değildi, fakat simdilerde herşey çok farklı” (kadın 40 +).</i>	<i>an adult male person the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</i>

Women’s Roles:

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*woman*” as:

- 1- an adult female person

Oxford dictionary defines the word “*role*” as:

- 1- the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation
- 2- a character in a play or film

In the responses the word “men`s roles” has been used in a context which parallels definition 1. For example the statement “Each society casts a role for woman and man from the cultural aspect. This role may evolve in time without any radical change. For example; as it is naturally accepted in all societies that role of woman in the house and as a mother, has evolved woman-mother-work- home the most. People accept certain roles involuntarily due to their existence. Unless the target group of advertisements is aliens, the adverts will show social roles of target groups (male 18-25). As another statement, “There is no fierce line between man and woman as it was in the past. Woman does not only perform housework. Woman also has roles in advertisements including various occupational groups (e.g. construction advertisements). While man performed in the advertisements presenting outside world, now they even perform in a biscuit advertisement (female 18-25)”. Moreover “As compared with the past, the role of woman in the house has become much content (female 40 +)”.

Table 28. Discourse Analysis of Code Representation (women`s roles)

<p>“Her toplum kültürel olarak kadın ve erkeğe bir rol biçer. Bu rol tarih boyunca gelişimler gösterebilir.Fakat köklü bir değişim gerçekleşmez.Örneğin; tüm toplumlarda doğal olarak benimsenmiştir.Kadının rolü anne ve ev ilişkisi tarih boyunca en fazla kadın- anne- iş- ev olarak gelişmiştir. Çünkü insanlar yaradılışı neticesiyle belirli rolleri istem dışı duygularla kabul eder. Reklam dünyasında ,hedef kitlesinin uzaylılar olmadığı sürece eserlerinde hedef kitlesinin toplumsal rollerini reklamlarında sergileyecektir (erkek 18-25).</p>	<p>an adult male person the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>
<p>“Bu gibi reklamlarda kadın ve erkek arasında geçmişe nazaran sert bir çizgi bulunmamaktadır. Kadın sadece ev işleriyle ilgili bir rol üstlenmiyor. Aynı zamanda birçok meslek gruplarıyla ilgili reklamlarda (örneğin, inşaat reklamı gibi) rol almaktadır. Geçmişte erkek dış dünya ile ilgili reklamlarda rol alırken artık günümüzde bir bisküvi reklamında bile rol almaktadır (kadın 18-25)”.</p>	<p>an adult male person the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>
<p>“Gecmiş yıllara nazaran kadının ev içindeki rolü daha rahat bir durum almıştır (kadın 40 +)”.</p>	<p>an adult male person the way in which someone or something is involved in a activity or situation</p>

Head/Leader/Authority:

In the responses the word “*Head/Leader/Authority*” has not been used in a context.

When the general responses to all questions are analyzed ranking least frequently, used expressions were observed to relate to Code 7 (sex) (which contains the words sexuality, sex). The following is the discourse analysis of these words individually.

Sexuality

In the responses the word “*sexuality*” has not been used in a context.

Sex:

In the responses the word “*sex*” has not been used in a context.

Discussion

This study has identified for the first time that the advertisement analysis carried out until today do not completely reflect the opinions of viewers. On the contrary of the statements given under the theoretical section delivering the advertisement findings, it is seen that the viewers have not perceived these elements. In compliance with the society structure in the development period, only the ‘old generation’ perceives the advertisements in parallel with the analysis findings while the new generation (18-25) has a far different perception than this profile. Since the new generation grew up with the advertisements designed by changing and developing technology, their discourses explicitly reflects that their perception of advertisement and gender representations in the advertisements are different compared with the old generation. This observation answers the first and second subsidiary questions of this study. Since the studies performed until today analyzed only advertisements, there is one result. However when a distinction is carried out on two different generations in this study, it shows that new generation has a different perception on the advertisements. As a general outcome of our study, it is found out that the perception of gender roles used in advertisement differs depending on the age and gender of people. The advertisements often use the attractions addressing the main emotions and needs of human. Therefore; gender roles and stereotypes are the most used codes of advertisements. The advertisement, due to its feature of reaching to large masses and transmitting the coded visuals over and over, has a significant role in the reinforcement of gender stereotypes in society. The discourses assessed under this study indicate that the dominant social stereotypes are in some way reflected in both generations but especially by women. On the contrary, the male population of this study has stayed insensitive to the perception of gender roles and just perceives the consumption in advertisements. These findings are then answers the third subsidiary question. The use of stereotypes in advertisements establishes a model especially for the children to learn their gender roles and affects the today’s young generation.

Finally; when the results reflected on the general profile are reviewed, the perception of Gender representation in television advertisements by Northern Cypriot viewers reflect a shift in the society in this respect towards a more gender sensitive structure. This justifies the accuracy of the hypothetical prediction.

Bibliography

- [1] Alberts, J.K., Nakayama, T. K.,and Martin, J. N. (2007). *Human communication in society*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [2] Altinel, H.(2002). Kozmetik reklamlarında kadın ve nesne ilişkisi. *Kocaeli Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Araştırma Dergisi*, 1, 52-64.
- [3] Akie N. Arima, **a.g.m.**, s:1, Mary Jiang Bresnan, “*Changing Gender Roles in Prime-Time Commercials in Malaysia, Japan, Taiwan, and the United States*”, **Sex Roles: A Journal of Research**, July 2001, s: 2, “*A Comparison of Cultural Values in Television Advertising in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Germany*”, <http://www.stephweb.com/capstone/t4.shtml>, 22.01.2006, Gayle Kaufman, **a.g.m.**, s: 443, Kenneh Allan, **a.g.m.**, s:2, Nimet Uray/Şebnem Burnaz, **a.g.m.**, s:85
- [4] Andersen, M.L (2006). *Thinking about women: sociological perspectives on sex and gender*. USA: Pearson Education.
- [5] Arima, A. (1996). Gender stereotypes in Japanese television Advertisements. *Sex Roles*, 49 (1), 81-90.
- [6] Axley, S. (1984). *Managerial and organizational communication in terms of the conduit metaphor*. Academy of Management Review.
- [7] Aziz, A. (2010). *İletişime Giriş*. 3. Basım. İstanbul: Hiperlink yayınları
- [8] Baran, S., Meyer, T. and McIntyre J. (1984). *Self, symbols and society: An introduction to mass communication*. New Jersey: Addison-Wesley.
- [9] Barthes, R. (1964). *Elements of semiology* (A.Lavers and C.Smith, Trans.). London: Cape.
- [10] Barthes, R. (1966). An introduction to the structural analysis of the narrative. *In R.Barthes (1977). Image, Music and text* (.S. Heath, Trans.). New York: Hill and Wan.
- [11] Barthes, R. (1967). *The fashion system* (M.Ward and R.Howard, Trans.). New York: Hill.
- [12] Baron, R.A and Bryne, D. (2000). *Social psychology*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.

- [13] Baudrillard Jean (1993). *The Transparency of Evil (1990)*. New York: Verso.
- [14] Belch, G.E and Belch, M.A. (1995). *Introduction to advertising and promotion: An integrated marketing communications perspective*. USA: Richard Irwin Inc.
- [15] Berelson, B., and Steiner, G. A. (1964). *Human Behavior*. New York: Harcourt, Brace and World.
- [16] Berger, J. (1991). *Ways of seeing*. New York and London: Penguin Books.
- [17] Boni, F. (2002). Framing media masculinities. *European Journal of Communication*, 17 (4), 465-78.
- [18] Breckler, S.J, Olson, J.M. and Wiggins, E.C. (2006). *Social psychology alive*. Belmont: Thomson Wadsworth.
- [19] Bruess, C. and Pearson, J. (1996). Gendered patterns in family communication. In J.Wood (Ed.), *Gendered relationships: A reader* (pp.59-78). Mountain View, CA: Mayfield.
- [20] Burke, Peter J., Jan E. Stets, and Maureen A. Pirog-Good. 1988. "Gender Identity, Self-Esteem, and Physical and Sexual Abuse in Dating Relationships." *Social Psychology Quarterly* 51: 272-285.
- [21] Burr, V. (1995). *An Introduction to social constructionism*. London and New York: Routledge.
- [22] Burr, V. (1998). *Gender and social psychology*. London and New York: Routledge.
- [23] Burton, G. (2005). *Media and society: Critical perspectives*. Berkshire and New York: Open University
- [24] Büyükkantarçioğlu, N. (2000). .Eleştirel söylem çözümlemesi ve toplumruhbilim bağlamında bir metin incelemesi: İnci Aral'ın gölgede kırk derece adlı öyküsü. In *Proceedings of first symposium on language, literature and stylistics* (pp 176-89). Denizli: Pamukkale University.
- [25] Carter, Cynthia and Steiner, Linda (2004) *Introduction to Critical Readings: Media and Gender*. London and New York: Routledge.
- [26] Chandler, D. (2002). *Semiotics: The basics*. London and New York: Routledge.
- [27] Cohen, B. (1963). *The press and foreign policy*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton.
- [28] Coltrane, S., and Adams, M. (1997) Work-family imagery and gender stereotypes: television and reproduction of difference. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 50,323-47.

- [29] Craig, Steve (1992). “Men’s Men and Women’s Women: How TV Commercials Portray Gender to Different Audiences”, **Issues and Effects of Mass Communication:Other Voices**, Ed:Robert Kemper, CA: Capstone Publishers, pp.89-100, 1992.
- [30] Dağtaş, B. (2009a). *Reklam, kültür ve toplum*. Ankara: Ütopya Yayınevi.
- [31] Dağtaş, B. and Dağtaş, E. (Eds.) (2009b). *Medya, tüketim kültürü ve yaşam tarzları: Türkiye medyasından örüntüler*. Ankara: Ütopya.
- [32] Dearing, James W., and Everett M. Rogers. (1996). *Agenda-Setting*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- [33] Dökmen, Z. (1999). Bem cinsiyet rolü envanteri kadınsılık ve erkeksilik ölçekleri Türkçe formunun psikometrik özellikleri. *Kriz Dergisi* , s.13
- [34] Dökmen, Z. (2004). *Toplumsal cinsiyet: Sosyal psikolojik açıklamalar*. İstanbul: Sistem Yayıncılık.
- [35] Eagly, Alice H. (1987). *Sex Differences in Social Behavior: A Social-Role Interpretation*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- [36] Elden, Muge and Kocabaş, Füsün (2004) , **Reklamcılık- Kavramlar, Kararlar, Kurumlar**, 5.Baskı, İletişim Yayınları, İstanbul, 2004, s:16
- [37] Erdoğan, E. and Akbulut, N. (2009). TV reklamlarında erkek imgesi. In C.Bilgili and N.
- [38] Feldmann, E., (1997), *Theorie der Massenmedien*, (2 Aufl), Munchen, E. Reinhardt.
- [39] Gerbner, George. (1980). Children and Power on Television: The Other Side of the Picture. In G. Gerbner, C.J. Ross, & E. Zigler (eds.), *Child Abuse: An Agenda for Action*. New York: Oxford University Press, pp. 239-248.
- [40] Gerbner, George. (1980). Death in Prime-Time: Notes on the Symbolic Functions of Dying in the Mass Media. *The Annals of The American Academy of Political and Social Science*, No. 447, pp. 64-70.
- [41] Gerbner, George, Larry Gross, Nancy Signorielli, and Michael Morgan. (1980). Aging with Television: Images on Television Drama and Conceptions of Social Reality. *Journal of Communication*, 30(1), 37-47.
- [42] Gerbner, George, Larry Gross, Nancy Signorielli, and Michael Morgan. (1980). Television Violence, Victimization and Power. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 23(5), 705-716.

- [43] Gerbner, George (1986). *The Symbolic Context of Action and Communication*. In Ralph L. Rosnow and Marianthi Georgoudi (Eds.), *Contextualism and Understanding in Behavioral Science*. New York: Praeger Publishers.
- [44] Ghauri, P., Gronhaug, K. and Kristianslund, I. (2005) *Research Methods in Business Studies*, 3rd ed., Prentice-Hall, Essex, UK.
- [45] Gledhill, C. (1997) 'Genre and Gender: The Case of Soap Opera'. In: Hall, S (ed) *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. London: Sage, pp. 337-86.
- [46] Gill, J. and Johnson, P. (1997) *Research Methods for Management*, London: Paul Chapman Publishing.
- [47] Gilligan, Carol. (1982). *In a Different Voice: Psychological Theory and Women's Development*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- [48] Goddard, Angela (1998). *The language of advertising*. London: Routledge.
- [49] Goffman, Erving (1976). *Gender in advertisements*. New York: Haper and Row.
- [50] Gökbulut, H. (2006). *Televizyon reklamlarının toplumsal rolleri pekiştirmesi* (Unpublished M.A Thesis). Ankara: Gazi University.
- [51] Güçlü, H.V. (2007). *Erkeklerle yönelik televizyon reklamlarının analizi* (Unpublished M.A Thesis).İstanbul: Marmara University.
- [52] Hall, S. (1997). *Representation: Cultural representations and signifying practices*. London: Sage.
- [53] Hall, S. (1997). 'The Work of Representation' In: Hall, S (ed) *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. London: Sage, pp. 13-74.
- [54] Hall, S. (1997) 'The Spectacle of the Other' In: Hall, S (ed) *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. London: Sage, pp. 223-90.
- [55] Harrison, A.C., and O'Neill, S.A. (2002). The development of children's gendered knowledge and preferences in music. *Feminism & Psychology*, 12, 145-152.
- [56] Hogg, M.A and Vaughan, G.M (2006). *Sosyal psikoloji* (İ. Yıldız and A.Gelmez,Trans.).Ankara: Ütopya.
- [57] Holsti, O. R. (1969) *Content Analysis for the Social Sciences and Humanities*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- [58] Hund, J. W., (1986), *Managing people at work*, Mc Graw Hill.

- [59] Illegard Johanna (2004), **Gender, Power and Work In TV Advertisements**, Master Thesis, Lund University, Department of Sociology, Spring 2004.
- [60] Infante, D. Rancer, A. & Womack, D. (1997). *Building communication theory* (3rd ed.). Prospect Heights, IL: Waveland.
- [61] Isobel Doole and Lowe Robin (2008) *Lowe International Marketing Strategy*, 5th Edition Mc Graw Hill.
- [62] Itzin, C. (1986) 'Media Images of Women: The Social Construction of Ageism and Sexism'. In: Wilkinson, S. (ed). *Feminist Social Psychology: Developing Theory and Practice*. Milton Keynes: Open University Press, pp. 119-34.
- [63] Jefkins, F. (1982). *Advertising Today*. 3rd edition, Glasgow: International Textbook Company.
- [64] Jhally, S. (1990). *The codes of advertising: Fetishism and the political economy of meaning in the consumer society*. London and New York: Routledge.
- [65] John, Fiske (1990) *Introduction to Communication Studies*. Routledge, 1990
- [66] Jones, M. (1991). Gender stereotyping in advertisements. *Teaching of Psychology*, 18, 231-233.
- [67] Judd, C. M., Smith, E. R. and Kidder, L. H. (1991) *Research Methods in Social Relations*, 6th ed., Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc., USA.
- [68] Lury, Celia (1996) *Consumer Culture*. (Blackwell, Oxford).
- [69] Katz, Phyllis A. (1986). "Gender Identity: Development and Consequences." Pp. 21-67 in
- [70] Richard D. Ashmore and Frances K. Del Boca (Eds.), *The Social Psychology of Female-Male Relations: A Critical Analysis of Central Concepts*. New York: Academic Press.
- [71] Kaufman, Gayle (1999) "*The Portrayal of Men's Family Roles in Television Commercials*", **Sex Roles: A Journal of Research**, Vol. 41, No. 5/6, 1999, s: 439
- [72] Kay, M. Mc., Davis, M. and Fanning, P. (2009). *Messages The Communication Skills Book*. 3rd ed. USA: New Harbinger Publications.
- [73] Kazazi, M., (1993), *Human relations and communication*, Ellin, Athens.
- [74] Kilbourne, Jean, (1995) "*Beauty and the Beast of Advertising*", 1995, http://www.medialit.org/reading_room/article40.html, 28.12.2012

- [75] Kocabaş, F. and Elden, M. (1997). *Reklamcılık: Kavramlar, kararlar ve kurumlar. İstanbul: İletişim.*
- [76] Kristeva, J. (1969). Word, dialogue and novell. (.A.Jardine, T. Gora and L.Roudiez, Trans.).In T. T. Moi (2005) (Ed.), *The Kristeva reader* (pp.34-61). New York: Colombia University Press.
- [77] Kutman, N. (2006). *Televizyon reklamlarında kullanılan arketipler ve otomobil reklamlarına uygulamaları* (Unpublished M.A Thesis). İstanbul: Marmara University.
- [78] Leary MR, Tangney JP, eds. (1981). *Handbook of Self and Identity*. New York: Guilford
- [79] Lester, P.M. and Ross, S.D. (2003) ‘Images that Injure: An Introduction’. In: Lester, P.M. and Ross, S.D. (eds). *Images That Injure: Pictorial Stereotypes in the Media*. (2nd ed). Westport, Connecticut: Praeger, pp. 1-4.
- [80] Linn, T. (2003) ‘Media Methods that Lead to Stereotypes’ In: Lester, P.M. and Ross, S.D. (eds). *Images That Injure: Pictorial Stereotypes in the Media*. (2nd ed). Westport, Connecticut: Praeger, pp. 23-7.
- [81] Locke, J. (1990) *Introduction to Communication Studies*. 2nd edition. Published by Routledge.
- [82] Maeroff, G Ed.). (1998). *Imagining education: The media and schools in America*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- [83] Malhotra, N. K. and Birks, D. F. (2007) *Marketing Research: An Applied Approach*, 3rd ed, Prentice-Hall, London, England.
- [84] Marchand, Roland (1986). **Advertising the American Dream**, University of California Pres, California, USA, 1986.
- [85] Marchbank, J. and Letherby, G. (2007). *Introduction to gender: sociological perspectives*. London: Longman.
- [86] Mayne,Iris “*The Inescapable Images:Gender and Advertising*”, **Equal Opportunities International**, Vol. 19, No.2/3/4, 2000, s:58
- [87] McClure, L. (1999). Wimpy boys and macho girls: Gender equity at the crossroads. *The English Journal*, 88, 78-82. doi: 10.2307/821583
- [88] McQuail, D. (1997). *Audience Analysis*. London: Sage.
- [89] McQuail, D. (1987). *Introduction to mass communication theory*. London: Sage. 284

- [90] Merriam Webster Dictionary, (2010) Merriam-Webster's Everyday Language Reference Set by Merriam-Webster (Corporate Author)
- [91] Miller, D.(1998). *A theory of shopping*. Oxford: Polity Press.
- [92] Mohan, M. (1989). *Advertising Management, Concept and Cases*. New Delhi: Tata AcGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited.
- [93] Mohd Hamdan Haji Adnan. (1991). Development and Anti-Development Messages in Film, Television and Advertising. *Media Asia*, 18 (2), 63-72.
- [94] Morgan, Michael and Nancy Rothschild. (1983). "Impact of the New Television Technology: Cable, Peers, and Sex-Role Cultivation in the Electronic Environment." *Youth and Society* 15: 33-50.
- [95] Morris, P. (2006, Summer). Gender in print advertisements: A snapshot of representations from around the world. *Media Report to Women*, 34, 13-20.
- [96] Nassif, A. and Gunter, B. (2008). Gender representation in television advertisements in Britain and Saudi Arabia. *Sex Roles*, 58 (11-12), 752-760.
- [97] Nowak, Caroline (2004) Cross-cultural analysis of television commercials in Sweden and Poland pg.49
- [98] Qualter, T. H.(1991). *Advertising and democracy in the mass age*. London: Mac Millan.
- [99] O'Guinn, T., Allen, C.T. and Semenik, R.J (1998). *Advertising*. Cincinnati, Ohio: South-Western College.
- [100] Oskay, Ü. (1992). *Kitle Haberlesme Teorilerine Giriş*, (Introduction of Mass Communication Theory). Istanbul: Der Yayınları. s.15
- [101] Özsoy, T.(2006). *Türk dergi reklamlarında kadın İmgesi Kullanımı :1971-2004 döneminin bir değerlendirmesi* (Unpublished M.A Thesis). Adana: Çukurova University.
- [102] Özyıldırım, İ.I. (2009). Reklam diline dilbilimsel bir bakış. In Ş. Yavuz (Ed.), *Reklamın toplumsal yansımaları ve yeni reklam biçimleri* (pp.61-73). Ankara: Ütopya.
- [103] Packard, V. (1957). *The Hidden Persuaders*. New York: Pocket Book Inc.
- [104] Petley, J., (2002). *Advertising*. Hodder Wayland, Great Britain.
- [105] Phillips, N. and Hardy, C. (2002). *Discourse analysis. Investigating processes of social construction*. Qualitative research methods series 50. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [106] Qualter, T. H.(1991). *Advertising and democracy in the mass age*. London: Mac Millan.

Sanson, A., & Bretherton, D. (2001). Conflict resolution : Theoretical and practical issues. In R. V. Wagner, D. Christie, & D. Winfer (Eds.), *Peace, conflict and violence: Peace psychology for the 21st century*. Prentice Hall.

[107] Sarantakos, S. (1993) *Social Research*. Macmillan Press, London.

[108] Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2007) *Research Methods for Business Students* 4th ed., London: Prentice Hall.

[109] Sekaran, U. (2003) *Research Methods for Business, 'A Skill Building Approach'*, 4th ed., New York: John Wiley & Sons.

[110] Severin, W. and Tankard, J. (1997). *Communication theories*. New York: Hastings House.

[111] Sharf, R.S. (2008). Feminist therapy: A multicultural approach. In *Theories of psychotherapy and counseling: Concepts and cases* (4th ed., pp. 435-477). Belmont, California: Brooks/Cole Publishing Co

[112] Sigelman, C.K. and Ryder, E.A. (2006). *Life-span human development* (5th ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth, Inc.

[113] Signorielli, N. McLeod, D. and Healy, E. (1994) 'Gender Stereotypes in MTV Commercials: The Beat Goes On'. *Journal of Broadcasting and Electronic Media*. 38 (1), pp. 91-102.

[114] Silbermann, A., (1973), *Soziologie der Massen Kommunikation*, Stuttgart.

[115] Silverman, D. (1993) *Interpreting Qualitative Data*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage

[116] Silverstone, R. (1999) *Why Study the Media*. Sage Publications

[117] Slater, D. (1997). *Consumer culture and modernity*. Cambridge: Polity.

[118] Smith, B.(2007). *The psychology of sex and gender*. Boston: Pearson.

[119] Spence, Janet T. (1985). "Gender Identity and Implications for Concepts of Masculinity and Femininity". Pp. 59-96 in T. B. Sonderegger (Ed.), *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation: Psychology and Gender*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press

[120] Spitzer, R.J. (Ed.). (1993). *Media and public policy*. Westport, CT: Praeger.

[121] Statt, David (1977). *Understanding the Consumer - A Psychological Approach*. London: Macmillan Press.

[122] Tayfur, G. (2008). *Reklamcılık*. Ankara: Nobel Yay.

[123] Taylor, F. (2003, July). Content analysis and gender stereotypes in children's books. *Teaching Sociology*, 31, 300-311. doi: 10.2307/3211327

- [124] Tekvar, S.O. (2006). *Dergi reklamlarında toplumsal cinsiyet göstergeleri: FHM ve Cosmopolitan reklamlarının karşılaştırmalı göstergebilimsel çözümlemesi* (Unpublished M.A Thesis). Ankara: Ankara University.
- [125] Timisi, Nilufer (2004) “*Reklamların Kadınlar Üzerindeki Etkileri:Reklamlarda Yer Alan Cinsellik Ögesi Oturumu*”, “*Reklamların İzleyiciler Üzerindeki Etkileri*” Paneli, RTÜK Yayın No:10, 1.Baskı, Ankara, Temmuz 2004, s: 29
- [126] Tolungüç, Ahmet (1999). *Publicity and Advertisement in Tourism* [in Turkish]. 1st Ed, Media Cat Yayınları, Ankara.
- [127] Turner, E., and Hovenden, F. (1997). How are we seen? Images of women in computing advertisements. In R. Lander and A. Adam (Eds.), *Women in computing* (pp.61- 70).Wiltshire, UK: Cromwell Pres, pp.61-70.
- [128] Uray, N.and Burnaz, Ş. (2003). An analysis of the portrayal of gender roles in Turkish TV advertisements. *Sex Roles*, 48 (1-2), 77-88.
- [129] Uzel, G.(2008). *Magazin basınında anne imgesi ve annelik: Kelebek magazin eki üzerine bir inceleme*(Unpublished M.A Thesis). Ankara: Ankara University.
- [130] van Dijk, T.(1998). *Ideology: A multidisciplinary approach*. London: Sage.
- [131] Weber, Robert Philip (1990). *Basic Content Analysis* (2nd ed.). Newbury Park, CA: Sage. p. 12.
- [132] Widdowson, H. G. (2007), *Discourse analysis*, Oxford, Oxford University Press
- [133] Williams, Raymond (1993). Advertising: The magic system: Problems in materialism and culture. In S. During (Ed.) *The cultural studies Reader* (p.329). London and New York: Routledge,.
- [134] William M. O'Barr (2006). Representations of Masculinity and Femininity in Advertisements:https://muse.jhu.edu/journals/advertising_and_society_review/v007/7.2unit07.html#_sourceref25 Advertising Educational Foundation
- [135] Wilson, J. and Wilson, S. (2001). *Mass media, mass culture: An introduction* (5th ed.). Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill.
- [136] Wimalasiri, Jayantha S. (2004). A cross- national study on children’s purchasing behavior and parental response, *Journal of Consumer Marketing* pg 275,281
- [137] Wimmer, R. and Dominick, J. (1991). *Mass media research: An introduction* (3rd ed.).

Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.

[138] Wodak, R. (2009). *The discourse-historical Approach*. In R.Wodak and M.Meyer (Eds), *Methods of critical discourse analysis* (pp.49-65). London: Sage.

[139] Wood, J.T. (2003). *Gendered lives: Communication, gender and culture*. Canada: Wadsworth Group. www.worldbank.org. Official web site of World Bank. Retrieved on 20 June 2011.

[140] Wood, J.T. (2010). *Communication Mosaics. An introduction to the field of communication*. Sixth Edition. Wadsworth Cengage Learning

[141] Wood, L. A & Kroger, R. O. (2000). *Doing discourse analysis. Methods for studying action in talk and text*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

[142] Yavuz, Ş. (2007). *Reklamları izlediniz*. Ankara: Ütopya.

[143] Yetkiner, Kansu N.(2004).Kadın bağı reklamlarında dilsel ve dilötesi aktarımlar üzerine bir inceleme. *Dilbilim Araştırmaları*, 89-110.

[144] Yıldızö Tuba: (2006). *Reklamda Cinsiyetin Kullanımı*, İstanbul.(Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Marmara Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü İletişim Bilimleri ABD.)

[145] Yılmaz, T. (2006). *Reklamlarda cinsiyetin kullanımı* (Unpublished M.A Thesis). İstanbul: Marmara University.

[146] Yüksel, E. (2006). Yılmaz Güney sinemasında kadın imgesi (Unpublished M.A Thesis). Ankara: Ankara University.